

UDK 338.1

Automation and Robotics as Components of a Digital Breakthrough

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Key words and phrases: automation; digital economy; digital transformation; economic development; robotics.

Abstract: The article deals with the issues of automation, robotics and digitalization of industrial enterprises. The conducted research made it possible to determine the role of automation and robotics in digital processes and their interrelation. The stages of the introduction of digital technologies in industrial production are presented. The obtained results were used as the basis for the development of an organizational and economic mechanism, an important element of which is to determine the characteristic features in solving the problems of digitalization of industrial enterprises.

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Modern theory and practice shows that the introduction of digital technologies is the foundation of the competitiveness of industrial enterprises, and, consequently, of the territories to which they belong.

Currently, digitalization is considered as a necessary basis for the competitiveness of the world economy of industrialized countries. Every year in these countries, the costs of conducting research and development in various fields related to digital industrial production processes are increasing.

In Russia, there are lower rates of development of digital technologies and a low level of costs for the development and creation of new products, the introduction of digital technologies, which has a negative impact on the competitiveness of the domestic industrial complex [1].

Under the conditions of sanctions, against the background of the general state of the economy in the country, enterprises are forced to optimize funds in order to survive. In the current situation, it is quite difficult to implement digital projects on a full scale.

The lack of available funds, inflation and a number of other factors do not allow enterprises to build long-term plans and invest in long-term projects. Therefore, representatives of industrial business are primarily interested in the introduction of quickly recouped projects, which should be justified by customer demand and needs and carry minimal costs for the enterprise both in terms of re-equipping existing production facilities and minimizing the cost of purchasing materials, raw materials, components for the production of a new product [4].

However, in the modern world it is impossible to do without constant attention to the issues of improving the production process. The growing needs, changing views on the quality and

technical characteristics of the products, cannot be met without significant attention to modern technologies in general and digital technologies in particular.

Despite the presence of certain barriers to the introduction of digital technologies, the study of industrial enterprises conducted by the authors showed the interest of representatives of industrial business in the processes of digitalization. As a result of the survey, it was revealed that most enterprises are planning to digitalize production processes. It should be noted that the most attractive, according to experts, for industrial enterprises is automation and robotization of production processes [2].

The study of world experience has shown that the introduction of robotics significantly changes the value chain of the product in the direction of reduction. It should be noted that currently about 10 % of production tasks are automated at the enterprises of the industrial complex. By 2030, it is predicted that investments in robotics will increase and their use in production will increase to 25–45 %.

According to Milton Garry, President of the International Federation of Robotics (**IFR**), despite the ongoing pandemic, the prospects for the robotics industry in the world are optimistic.

The most promising markets for industrial robots are the regions of Asia. The primacy in this market belongs to China, Japan is in second place, followed by India, which has been able to double the number of industrial robots over the past 5 years. In Europe, the recovery of the robotics market is slow. The leader of automation and robotics is Germany. In Russia, the situation on the industrial robotics market is ambiguous. Experts of the National Association of Robotics Market Participants (**NASR**) believe that Russia lags behind developed countries by 7–10 years.

At industrial enterprises in Russia, the density of robotization of production is more than 20 times lower than the global average. According to IFR statistics, there are three industrial robots per 10,000 workers in Russia, while in countries with a high level of digitalization there are more than 100.

Despite the pessimistic statistics of international agencies, it should be noted that in general, the situation in Russia can be assessed positively, because for several years there has been an annual growth in the robotics market. First of all, this is due to the processes of digitalization of the industrial complex of the Russian Federation.

It should be noted that the substitution of the concepts of automation, robotization and digitalization is very often observed at the enterprises of the industrial complex. However, neither automation nor robotization is digitalization in itself. Automation should now be considered as an integral element of robotization and digitalization [1].

To consider automation and robotics in a digital focus, an enterprise needs an effective management system, artificial intelligence and a team of specialists that ensure the effectiveness of digital processes, since digitalization provides a systematic approach to the use of digital resources to increase labor productivity, competitiveness and economic development in general [3].

In her studies, A. Vichugova identifies five differences between automation and digitalization, which include:

- degree of integration of processes and data;
- virtualization of the main production facility;
- the nature of data management;
- production management procedure;
- flexibility of corporate culture.

With a more detailed study of the differences presented above, it becomes obvious that

automation is part of digitalization, but not synonymous. In order for automation within digital processes to be effective, in our opinion, complex and step-by-step work is necessary.

When implementing digital technologies in general, automation and robotics in particular, it is important to control and comply with all requirements, calculated actions and consumption rates. This stage is the most time-consuming and difficult.

Before planning the introduction of digital innovations (automation, robotics), it is necessary to conduct market research in order to identify new requirements for goods and the need for new types of products.

Based on the data obtained, it is necessary first of all to exclude technologies that will not significantly affect the satisfaction of market conditions in the areas identified as a result of market analysis, while the new equipment should be universal, with the possibility of re-equipment with minimal costs.

At the next stage of choosing the direction of automation, it is necessary to conduct a technological audit of the enterprise in order to identify the possibility of introducing digital technologies and the possibility of their integration with the equipment available at the enterprise.

The third stage in the implementation of automation is the analysis of raw materials and materials costs. The ideal option for the company would be the use of existing stocks of raw materials and semi-finished products or the purchase of identical materials.

Next, it is necessary to conduct a more detailed analysis of the automation project and decide on the final version.

The implementation of digital innovations should take place under strict control of all stages. If deviations are detected, timely work is necessary to eliminate the problems that have arisen.

To assess the effectiveness of a digital innovation project, it is necessary to conduct a comparative assessment of the options in terms of their profitability, cost and timing of implementation.

The effectiveness of digitalization should be assessed by analyzing commercial, budgetary and national economic efficiency. It is advisable to consider the impact of digital innovations not only on the economic, but also on the environmental and social component of both the enterprise itself and the territory.

Thus, the management of automation and robotics as elements of digitalization is a complex multi-stage process that includes the management and coordination of information, labor, material and other resources throughout the time of using digital technology through the application of a system of modern methods and approaches in management.

The study was carried out with the financial support of the Russian Foundation for Basic Research for research project No. 20-010-00219.

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Автоматизация и роботизация как составные элементы цифрового прорыва

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Ключевые слова и фразы: автоматизация; роботизация; цифровая трансформация; цифровая экономика; экономическое развитие.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены вопросы автоматизации, роботизации и цифровизации предприятий промышленного комплекса. Проведенное исследование позволило определить роль автоматизации и роботизации в цифровых процессах и их взаимосвязь. Представлены этапы внедрения цифровых технологий в промышленное производство. Полученные результаты были положены в основу разработки организационно-экономического механизма, важным элементом которого является определение характерных особенностей в решении задач цифровизации предприятий промышленного производства.

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